

DIFFERENT AND SIMILAR ASPECTS OF ISLAMIC BANKING FROM TRADITIONAL BANKS

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Annotation: Commercial banks are those financial institutions which accept and advancing loan on interest basis. They perform different functions as leasing, agency function etc. They have different types of accounts, locker facility for customers. Commercial banking is based on manmade rules and focus on interest financing. Islamic banking, also referred to as Islamic finance or Shariah-compliant finance, refers to financial activities that adhere to Shariah (Islamic law). Two fundamental principles of Islamic banking are the sharing of profit and loss and the prohibition of the collection and payment of interest by lenders and investors. In this article we can discuss about different and similar aspects of Islamic banking from traditional banks.

Keywords: Islamic banking systems, traditional banks, commercial bank, functions, rules, different points, similar aspects.

Islamic banks perform functions as commercial banks but they follow the rules of Islamic Shariah board. Islamic banking is the interest free banking. They follow the Islamic modes of finance Mudarabah, Musharaka, Ijarah etc. In Islamic banking Islamic rules are following. Islamic banking started in Pakistan to minimize and eliminate the interest. Conventional banks rely on Manmade principles and focuses on maximization of profit. The fundamental function of conventional banking is lending money and takes it back with high interest including profit. Conventional banks are in large number than Islamic banks that don't share profit and loss with customers. Islamic banks share profit and loss with its customers and depositors. This sharing gives more strong ground to Islamic Banking. Islamic Banking working base on interest free banking. But conventional banks base on Interest-based techniques and principles. One of the primary differences between

conventional banking systems and Islamic banking is that Islamic banking prohibits usury and speculation. Shariah strictly prohibits any form of speculation or gambling, which is referred to as maisir. Shariah also prohibits taking interest on loans.

Conventional banks	Islamic banks
1. Time value is the basis for charging interest on capital	1. Profit on exchange of goods & services is the basis for earning profit
2. The expanded money in the money market without backing the real assets, result deficit financing	2. Balance budget is the outcome of no expansion of money
3. Interest is charged even in case, the organization suffers losses. Thus no concept of sharing loss	3. Loss is shared when the organization suffers loss
4. While disbursing cash finance, running finance or working capital finance, no agreement for exchange of goods & services is made	4. The execution of agreement for the exchange of good & services is must, while disbursing funds under Salam & Istisna contracts
5. Due to non-existence of goods & services behind the money while disbursing funds, the	5. Due to existence of goods & services no expansion of money takes place and thus no inflation is created

expansion of money takes place, which creates inflation	
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- Islamic banking, also referred to as Islamic finance or Shariah-compliant finance, refers to finance or banking activities that adhere to Shariah (Islamic law).
- Two fundamental principles of Islamic banking are the sharing of profit and loss and the prohibition of the collection and payment of interest by lenders and investors.
- Islamic banks make a profit through equity participation, which requires a borrower to give the bank a share in their profits rather than paying interest.

Some conventional banks have windows or sections that provide designated Islamic banking services to their customers. Islamic banking is grounded in the tenets of the Islamic faith as they relate to commercial transactions. The principles of Islamic banking are derived from the Quran—the central religious text of Islam. In Islamic banking, all transactions must comply with Shariah, the legal code of Islam (based on the teachings of the Quran). The rules that govern commercial transactions in Islamic banking are referred to as *fiqh al-muamalat*. Employees of institutions that abide by Islamic banking are trusted to not deviate from the fundamental principles of the Quran while they are conducting business. When more information or guidance is necessary, Islamic bankers turn to learned scholars or use independent reasoning based on scholarship and customary practices.

One of the primary differences between conventional banking systems and Islamic banking is that Islamic banking prohibits usury and speculation. Shariah strictly prohibits any form of speculation or gambling, which is referred to as

maisir. Shariah also prohibits taking interest on loans. In addition, any investments involving items or substances that are prohibited in the Quran—including alcohol, gambling, and pork—are also prohibited. In this way, Islamic banking can be considered a culturally distinct form of ethical investing.

To earn money without the typical practice of charging interest, Islamic banks use equity participation systems. Equity participation means if a bank loans money to a business, the business will pay back the loan without interest and instead give the bank a share in its profits. If the business defaults or does not earn a profit, then the bank also does not benefit. In general, Islamic banking institutions tend to be more risk-averse in their investment practices. As a result, they typically avoid business that could be associated with economic bubbles.

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